

OPTIMIZATION OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION SERVICE AT MALINAU HOSPITAL

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10158613](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10158613)

Abstract

Serving the community is one of the important tasks or functions, especially in sub-districts that carry out their government functions. Public service is a very important factor in government management in government tasks because it involves very broad aspects of life. Public services are always associated with activities carried out by a person, group of people, or an organization to bring assistance and convenience to the community to achieve certain goals. Public services are becoming increasingly important because they are always in contact with people with different interests and goals. Thus, public service organizations can be run or not run by the government. In terms of government organizations providing services, the most important thing is how to provide assistance and convenience to the community to meet their needs and interests. This study aims to determine community satisfaction with public service administration at Malinau Hospital. This study uses a quantitative method with a Likert Scale measurement to assess community satisfaction surveys. The results of the community satisfaction index at Malinau Hospital are included in the total index of 3.17 with a survey value of 79.28 so that it can be categorized as performance quality B (Good). Service that pleases the community is one indicator of the success of every organization/public sector in providing services to the community.

Keywords: Administration, Public Service, Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government is a refinement of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 22 of 1999 and Law No. 32 of 2004 concerning the Law of the Republic of Indonesia. Regional administrations emphasize self-management in provinces and cities. The implementation of regional self-management aims to bring services closer to the community. The government's role has shifted from being an enforcer to a facilitator, promoter, and regulator of development programs. The development program is adapted to the potential and conditions of each region. Provinces and municipalities, in carrying out government functions, especially in implementing regional autonomy, are given rights and are obliged to fulfill obligations (Jaya et al., 2021).

The regional government is a very important part of the framework of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and this can be seen in Article 18 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia as amended, which states that this is the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia. Each district and each city has a regional government regulated by law so that, in essence, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia attaches great importance to the regional government, and each regional government is given regional autonomy (regional autonomy) (Muriawan et al., 2020). In public services, service is fulfilling service needs as determined by law. Public services include "providing a service (serving) the needs of people or people interested in the organization according to the basic rules and procedures that have been

established."(Bahari & Herawaty, 2023). Meanwhile, on the other hand, it is said that public service is the effort of a person and/or a group of people or a certain body to provide support and convenience to the community in achieving certain goals and targets. (Muriawan et al., 2020)

Serving the community is one of the important tasks or functions, especially in sub-districts that carry out their government functions. Public service is a very important factor in government management in government tasks because it involves very broad aspects of life. Public services are always associated with activities carried out by a person, group of people, or an organization to bring assistance and convenience to the community to achieve certain goals. Public services are becoming increasingly important because they are always in contact with people with different interests and goals. Thus, public service organizations can be run or not run by the government. In terms of government organizations providing services, the most important thing is providing assistance and convenience to the community to meet their needs and interests (Nurdin, 2019).

A hospital is a medical facility that provides medical services in the form of inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services. The hospital as a health unit generates a large amount of data, which requires good management to produce useful information. In today's modern era, the hospital has developed a Hospital Administration Information System, or what can be called SIARS, which helps provide health services for people who wish to seek treatment (Putra & Darmawan, 2021). Various activities related to Hospital services are: Receiving patients, medical services (doctors), nurse health services, medical support services, health services, catering, and financial management (Suryawati et al., 2006).

Malinau Hospital is located in Malinau District, North Kalimantan Province. Malinau Hospital was inaugurated on January 19, 2005, by the Governor of East Kalimantan H.Suwarna Abdul Fatah, with the status of a Type D Hospital with a capacity of 20 beds, 2 Specialists, 3 General Practitioners, and 44 people Employees (31 civil servants and 13 honorary workers). RSUD Malinau became a hospital with a Regional Public Service Agency (BLUD) status on 29 June 2010 December 2012 by the Decree of the Minister of Health No. HK.03.05/I/195/12 Concerning Hospital Classification. RSUD Malinau upgraded the Hospital Class to Class C with a Capacity of 114 Beds. And it was continued with the Accreditation of Malinau Hospital with Accreditation of 5 Service Fields with the Designation Number KARS-SERT/196/XII/2011. Malinau Hospital has met the Hospital Accreditation Standards and was declared to have passed the Plenary Level with the KARS-SERT/Per/012/II/2022 certificate number. This study aims to determine community satisfaction with public service administration at Malinau Hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This study uses a quantitative method with a Likert Scale measurement to assess community satisfaction surveys (Sekaran, 2006). Research respondents were asked to determine their level of agreement with the statements provided. Elements of a survey of community satisfaction conducted on RSU Malinau refers to the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform Number 14 of 2017 concerning Guidelines for Compiling Public Satisfaction Surveys for Public Administration Units, which consists of 9 (nine) elements, namely: 1) service

requirements; 2) service procedures; 3) service time; 4) fees/tariffs; 5) service products; 6) competence of service providers; 7) behavior of service providers; 8) complaint handling; 9) facilities and infrastructure as well as suggestions and input (Indonesia, 2017).

Respondents in this study were randomly selected, with 135 respondents who visited the Malinau Hospital. The tool used in this community satisfaction survey uses a questionnaire designed in the form of a statement answer to each service element question in the questionnaire in the form of multiple choice questions. The level of service quality is assessed with four answer choices 1) not good; 2) not good; 3) good; and 4) very good. In addition, there are qualitative questions in the form of statements of suggestions and additional input.

The formula for calculating the index is prepared by referring to the provisions in PERMENPAN-RB No. 14 of 2017. To calculate the IKM, previously determined the "weighted average value" of each service element which was determined by the formula:

$$\text{Average Value Weight - Weighted Average} = \frac{\text{Total Weights}}{\text{Total Element}} = \frac{1}{X} = N$$

Because the survey uses all service elements/variables (variables), the weighted average values are:

$$\text{Average Value Weight - Weighted Average} = \frac{1}{9} = 0,111$$

Furthermore, the weighted average value is used to calculate the value of IKM, namely by using the formula:

$$IKM = \frac{\text{Total of Perceived Value Per Element}}{\text{Total Elements Filled}} \times \text{Weighted Average}$$

To facilitate the interpretation of the SKM assessment, which is between 25 and 100. The results of the assessment are converted to a base value of 25, with the formula:

$$IKM \text{ Service Unit} \times 25$$

Furthermore, the IKM value is divided into several assessment criteria as follows:

Table 1: Perceived Value, Interval Value, Conversion Interval Value, Service Quality and Service Unit Performance

Perceived Value	Interval Value	Conversion Interval Value	Service Quality	Service Unit Performance
1	1,00 – 2,5996	25 – 64,99	D	Not good
2	2,6 – 3,064	65, - 76,60	C	Not good
3	3,0644 – 3,532	76,61 – 88,30	B	Good
4	3,5324 – 4,0	88,31 – 100,00	A	Very good

Source: PERMENPAN-RB No. 14 of 2017

The data analysis is quantitative to show an index or a numerical description of service conditions. Further analysis was conducted qualitatively and descriptively by presenting data obtained through interviews and field observations. The qualitative

analysis that was carried out was a description as well as an in-depth analysis of the quantitative analysis that was carried out previously.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of research and discussion of community satisfaction survey results at Malinau Hospital, North Kalimantan Province.

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Man	40	30
Woman	95	70
Total	135	100
Age		
17-25 Years	25	19
26-36 Years	35	26
36-45 Years	40	30
46-55 Years	22	16
>56 Years	13	10
Total	135	100
Education		
SD	19	14
Junior high school	14	10
Senior high school	52	39
College	50	37
Total	135	100
Work		
civil servant	31	23
Self-employed	5	4
Private	25	19
Farmers/Laborers/Fishermen	10	7
IRT	42	31
Retired	5	4
Not Working/Not Yet Working/Student	13	10
Honorary Officer	4	3
Total	135	100

Source: Research Data, 2023

Based on Table 2 of the characteristics of the respondents who visited the Malinau Hospital in August 2023, the majority were women, as many as 95. Most respondents are 36-45 years old, with the majority of high school and university education. As for the work, the respondents of this study are housewives.

Table 3: Results of the Community Satisfaction Index at Malinau Hospital

No	Service Elements	Index Score	conversion IKM	Service Performance Quality
1	Condition	3,1	78,52	B (Good)
2	Procedure	3,0	75,93	C (Not Good)
3	Time	2,9	72,59	C (Not Good)
4	Fees/Tariffs	3,5	87,59	B (Good)
5	Service Products	3,2	80,19	B (Good)
6	Executor Competency	3,2	80,93	B (Good)
7	Executing Behavior	3,2	80,00	B (Good)
8	Facilities and infrastructure	2,9	72,78	C (Not Good)

9	The handling of complaints	3,4	85,74	B (Good)
Index		3,17		
SKM value			79,28	
Performance Quality				B (Baik)

Source: Research Data, 2023

Based on the data presented in Table 3 regarding the results of the community satisfaction index at Malinau Hospital, it is included in the total index of 3.17 with a survey value of 79.28 to be categorized as B (Good) performance quality. As for the several elements surveyed, 3 elements had a service performance quality value of C (Not Good), as the service procedures provided received many unfavorable responses from respondents with an index value of 3.0. Many respondents also felt that the waiting time for service delivery could have been better, with an index value of 2.9. In addition, respondents rated the facilities and infrastructure at the hospital as not good, with an index value of 2.9.

Table 4: Suggestions and Feedback

No	Input Items	Frequency	Percentage
1	There isn't any	89	66
2	Orderliness in service time is improved	14	10
3	Service optimized again	13	10
4	Improvement of Human Resources (HR)	6	4
5	Service is good and satisfying	6	4
6	Improved facilities and infrastructure	5	4
7	Cleanliness is improved	2	1

Source: Research Data, 2023

Apart from filling out the questions in the form of multiple choice, the respondents also provided suggestions and input for the improvement of Malinau Hospital to be even better. Respondents who provide input include the need for order in service time, service optimization, human resources, facilities and infrastructure that need to be improved, and cleanliness that needs to be improved again. There were 6 (4%) respondents who felt the services provided by Malinau Hospital were good and satisfying.

Public service is a series of activities carried out by service providers to meet the community's needs. Public service is the provision of services by the government, private parties on behalf of the government, or private parties to the community, with or without payment, to meet the needs or interests of the community. By definition, public service is the provision of services (serving) the needs of people or communities who are interested in the organization in accordance with the established rules and procedures. (Arini & Hariyoko, 2023). According to the law of numbers. 25 of 2009 concerning public services defines public services as: "Public services are activities or series of activities to meet service needs as determined by law for all citizens and residents for goods, services, and administrative services provided by service delivery agencies. Public". From these definitions, it can be concluded that public service provides services to the community following established laws (Safi'i & Sulistiadi, 2020).

Public service performance in Indonesia is led by an independent organization of the executive, embracing the Republic of Indonesia. Article 1 of Law No. 37 of 2008 regulates the control of the mediator's public service. In this article, it is explained that

the Ombudsman is a state institution that has the authority to protect the implementation of public services carried out by state regulatory agencies and the government, including institutions such as BUMN, BUMD, BHMN, private organizations, and individuals. Responsible for providing public services. The characteristics of good public service include the following elements: Availability of good staff, Availability of good facilities and infrastructure, Responsible for each customer from start to finish, Able to serve quickly and precisely, Having the ability to communicate, Have good knowledge and capacity, Try to understand customer needs, Be able to create trust with customers (Hajar et al., 2022).

Existing public services should work to reduce (if not eliminate) the role gap between central and local implementing organizations. The number of employees/equipment available is appropriate, not less and not medium and high, so that the facility can reach the target. The services provided must also bring administrative apparatus closer to the community as customers. The low quality of public services is caused by several things: the monopoly context, in this case, because there is no competition from non-government public service providers, the government does not have strong incentives to increase the quantity, quality, or delivery of these services; environmental pressure, when environmental factors greatly affect the performance of service organizations in transactions and interactions between the environment and public institutions; heritage culture, where the culture of public service providers in Indonesia is still very much tied to the political and cultural traditions of the local community which are often not good and violate established regulations (Putri, 2022).

The results of the community satisfaction index at Malinau Hospital are included in the total index of 3.17 with a survey value of 79.28 so that it can be categorized as performance quality B (Good). Service that pleases the community indicates the success of every organization/public sector, such as providing services to the community. For this reason, to provide maximum public services, every public organization must have a model in the service mechanism, namely efficient and effective services and placing the community as service users to be served as well as possible. (Jarnawansyah, 2019; Tumilantouw et al., 2019).

The quality of district government public services will give district government agencies a good image in the eyes of the community and bring satisfaction to the community. Community satisfaction originating from the services provided by the government under it must be continuous, sustainable, and increasing, following the needs and needs of the community, which are also increasingly developing and complex. That is, the ways and systems of public service respond to satisfaction today may be different from the response of society tomorrow, and so on. Changes and adjustments to the system and the right way to provide public services to current needs are a form of district government innovation in optimizing public services. The services provided must be efficient. They should be relatively inexpensive (Kurlinda et al., 2023; Riska Agustina, 2022).

CONCLUSION

The results of the community satisfaction index at Malinau Hospital are included in the total index of 3.17 with a survey value of 79.28 so that it can be categorized as performance quality B (Good). Service that pleases the community is one indicator of the success of every organization/public sector in providing services to the community.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the Malinau Hospital for agreeing to be the site of this research and the Borneo Tarakan University LPPM for providing funds so that this research can be carried out.

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